
**BRILLIANT WORKS OF GREAT POET-TRANSLATOR BASED ON
TURKIC LITERATURE**

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Abstract: This article deals with the great afford of poet-translator, Sergei Nikolaevich Ivanov, who made enormous contribution to the development of art of translation. S.N. Ivanov was one of the researchers who did the translation of the works of great Turkic poet. Sergei Nikolaevich Ivanov let people to know the original meaning of Alisher Navoi’s aphorisms and sayings.

Key words: Orientalist-philologist, spiritual culture, eastern poetry, tuyug, poetic translation, internal rhymes, caesura(pause).

Introduction: Orientalist-philologist, historian of Turkic studies, teacher, poet-translator - among these four main areas of activity of Sergei

Nikolaevich Ivanov, his work as a poet-translator became a brilliant page in the history of the Russian and Uzbek art of poetic translation and in the life of world literature. This one is his activity was addressed to a wide range of readers and allowed them to get acquainted with the best achievements of the centuries-old spiritual culture of the peoples of the East. The merits of Sergei Nikolaevich in this the field is truly great - he gave new life, already in Russian, to little-known and previously inaccessible masterpieces of eastern poetry, enriching thereby native Russian culture and the world heritage of translation.

S. N. Ivanov was a member of the Union of Writers of Russia, fellow translators elected him chairman of the literary translation section of St. Petersburg Writers' Organization. Regularly at meetings in this section, within the walls of the House of Writers or the House of Scientists, he gave a reading of his new translations, and almost always these readings were also attended by students and graduates of the Department of Turkic Philology.

Literature analysis and methodology:

Deep scientific study of many Turkic languages, extensive general knowledge in the field of Oriental studies - all this was a reliable fact and the unique basis on which Sergei’s talent was revealed as a poet-translator of Turkic poetry. He published numerous translations from ancient Turkic languages, Azerbaijani, Tatar, Turkish, Turkmen, Uzbek and Old Uzbek, as well as from the Persian and Tajik languages, amounting to two dozen ethical books. In the history of Russian poetic translation,

Professor Ivanov was the first to recreate the so-called tuyug - Turkic quatrains with homonymous rhyme, remaining to this day unsurpassed by anyone in this area.

In his written interview with the author of these lines in 1987, Sergei

Nikolaevich said that he began to engage in poetic translation in 1960. According to him, the most significant place in his translations is occupied by classical Uzbek poetry - the works of Alisher Navoi, Gadai, Atai, Munis Khorezmi, Lutfi, Hafiz Khorezmi, Babur, Mashrab, Furkat, works by women poets Nadira, Uvaisi, Dilshod, Zebunnisa, Anbar-atyn. In 1969, for the anniversary of Alisher Navoi, his wonderful poem “The Language of Birds” was translated, forming the 8th volume of the collected works of this poet in Russian. In this 10-volume collected works of Alisher Navoi, a large number of poetic translations of S. N. Ivanov are also presented in volumes 1 and 2 (Tashkent, 1968 and 1969). This is Navoi’s lyrics: tuyugi, kyta, rubai, ghazals. Among the Azerbaijani poets, the translator was attracted by Imadeddin Nasimi, who, according to S.N. Ivanov, gave outstanding examples of lyricism. He also said that the work on translating the beautiful poems of the Turkmen poet Magtymguly brought him great creative joy.

Classical and modern Uzbek lyrics translated by S. N. Ivanova compiled several books and collections, including a whole cycle of works dedicated to the work of Alisher Navoi, the founder of the Uzbek literary language and classical Uzbek literature. To this cycle is adjacent to the study and translation of the lyrics of Uzbek poets, who worked over five centuries: “Hamza Hakim-zade Niyazi: Selected Works” (L., 1970) - poems by a poet of the twentieth century, “In imperishable beauty appears: Uzbek classical lyrics of the 15th – 20th centuries” (M., 1977), “Blood Word: Translations from Uzbek Poetry” (Tashkent, 1981), three books published by the Academy of Sciences of the UzSSR in the series “Selected Lyrics of the East” and representing the work of Uzbek poetesses: “Nadira: Selected poems” (Tashkent, 1979), “Uvaisi: Favorites” (Tashkent, 1981),

“Zebunnisa, Dilshod, Anbar-atyn” (Tashkent, 1983). For his activities, S. N. Ivanov was awarded the titles “Honored Worker of Culture of the UzSSR” (1968) and “Honored Worker of Science of the UzSSR” (1981).

The latest poetic book by S. N. Ivanov, the collection “Alisher Navoi:

Favorites” was published in 1996 with an introductory article by the translator himself [2]. This article has independent scientific, theoretical and applied significance. This collection is special: it includes new, previously unpublished translations of 185 Navoi gazelles, and the translation these gazelles are made on the basis of new principles that were developed and formulated by Sergei Nikolaevich. The main thing in these new principles is the presence in the ghazal of internal rhymes on caesura(pause). This author’s technique prevents the verse from collapsing in Russian poetic perception. In the same time this technique has its basis and

justification in the fact that many Uzbek – and more broadly – Turkic gazelles have such internal rhymes. Turkic poets in this way turned a long beyt couplet into a quatrain familiar to Turkic ears, which corresponded

Turkic poetic perception.

Main part: In the artistic heritage of S. N. Ivanov, it is necessary to especially highlight his translations of three epic poems - the pinnacle phenomena of classical Turkic-language poetry: 1) the 15th century poem “The Language of Birds” by Alisher Navoi (Tashkent,1970) [1], 2) poem of the 11th century “Blessed Knowledge” by Yusuf Balasaguni (M.,1983) [15] and 3) the poem of the 13th century “The Tale of Yusuf” by Kul Gali (Kazan,1985) [12]. These three works, without a doubt, now constitute the glory of Russian oriental studies and Russian translation art. Patriarch of Russian Turkic Studies, Academician A. N. Kononov in a conversation with the author of these lines regarding these translations in 1986, I noticed that in addition to S. N. Ivanov, he does not know anyone in the world who could translate these ancient poetic texts with the same philological precision and artistic perfection. Two of these works are “Blessed Knowledge” and “Language of birds” - published by the Russian Academy of Sciences in the series "Literary Monuments" (1983 and 1993, respectively), in 1990 "Blessed Knowledge" republished in the Great Series of the "Poet's Library".

It can be argued that S. N. Ivanov, as a poet-translator, raised creative bar in the field of poetic translation of classical Turkic poetry to such a height that, obviously, will forever remain inaccessible to other translators. One of the first such works can be considered the introductory article Sergei Nikolaevich to the collection of works by Alisher Navoi, who was published in 1965 in the small series “Library of the Poet” [5]. This job contains a deep and comprehensive analysis of the literary heritage of Alisher Navoi, a study of his poetry, its figurative, poetic and formal features. This kind of work is the reliable basis on which the poet-translator can continue to work fruitfully.

Some of S. N. Ivanov’s works were published in the periodical collections “The Craft of Translation”, in particular, here in 1975 appears article of fundamental importance “Alisher Navoi’s poem “Language of birds”: Experience of translation interpretation" [7]. It finds its final expression of the translator’s theoretical position that the rhythmic equivalent of the Turkic verse should be sought in the trisyllabic Russian sizes. As a result of his scientific research, Sergei Nikolaevich developed new principles of translation of Turkic ghazals, which are formulated in theses “On the question of the principles of Russian translation of Alisher Navoi’s gazelles” [10]. It seems that it would be correct to collect all these works under one cover, especially since they represent research not only on theory of translation, but also on the theory

and history of classical Turkic language literature, being in its entirety a unique textbook in this areas of knowledge.

Historical stylistics of the Turkic languages to the present day practically not developed, and not a single dictionary gives the stylistic characteristics of the Turkic vocabulary of the medieval period. In Turkic studies, apart from the works of S.N. Ivanov, problems have not even been raised yet semantic aura (semantic load) and stylistic affiliation of the poetic dimensions of classical Turkic poetry. Therefore, a solution to this problem is possible only on the basis of special philological knowledge and a developed sense of language, which appears only as a result of being well-read in such texts. Knowledge of the stylistic characteristics of the original allowed S. N. Ivanov in his translation practice, it is justified to use the functional stylistic stratification of modern Russian vocabulary, and special rhythms and co-syntactic techniques, and strictly defined poetic meters to recreate the artistic style of the original. Sergei Nikolaevich’s professional knowledge has always been at the heart of this re-creation Turkologist scientist, in particular, knowledge gained by many years of experience style of distinctive features characteristic of the medieval language Turkic poetry.

Results and discussion: For ancient oriental poetry, which was translated by S. N. Ivanov, in general, it is characterized by a very unique poetic aesthetics. As mentioned above, the manifestations of this aesthetics - both formal and substantive - can only be seen through a scientific study of the original and its full understanding. That is why attempts to create a high-quality poetic translation by rhyming interlinearly in this case cannot be creatively fruitful. Translations by S. N. Ivanov are characterized by a scientific and artistic style, based on conscious consideration of all the formal and substantive features of the original. But to this is always added something without which true poetic translation is unthinkable - empathy, co-creation translator, his emotional penetration into the spiritual biography of the author. Thanks to this, the literary works of S. N. Ivanov represented as being examples of high art.

All of the above mentioned allows us to characterize the artistic heritage of Sergei Nikolaevich Ivanov as one of the pinnacle achievements of the art of Russian poetic translation and as a unique phenomenon in history Russian translated literature. The activity of the orientalist scientist S. N. Ivanov as a poet and translator is a direct outcome of classical oriental studies into practice, into the real modern and future existence of many people; This first-class popularization of a huge amount of knowledge, accumulated by modern science about the East. Now, when the task of reviving national culture is so urgent, such a direct connection between humanities science and the spiritual life of society acquires a special value and once again confirms the significance and high meaning of the literary work of S. N. Ivanov.

The works of Sergei Nikolaevich Ivanova are still relevant in the field of studying linguistics and translation theory. Having been worked on the translation of Turkic languages, the poet-translator laid the foundation for the study of the aphorisms of Alisher Navoi and his work is still considered one of the important resources for the research works of oriental investigators. Seeing his translations we realize how the scientist was smart in word choice of expressing the real soul of sayings of A.Navoi.

Ко'п демак со'зга маг'рурлик,

Ва ко'п уемак нафсга ма'мурлик.

Велеричность - гордость болтуна,

В обжорстве - низость алчности видна.

In the given translation one can notice a great choice of words that might be used in equal line with the words of Turkic poet, even the phrases were selected according to time of the poet had lived.

“Велеричность - гордость болтуна,” – This part of saying means that a person who has good oratorical talent and the ability to express his thoughts convincingly in words may be proud of his eloquence, which can sometimes lead to overconfidence and exaggeration of his abilities in conversation. The meaning of the supposed translation is similar to what was meant by A.Navoi.

“В обжорстве - низость алчности видна.”- The second part of saying means that when a person eats too much or consumes large portions of food, his low greed and insatiability become apparent. That is, through excessive food consumption, his greed and base instincts become visible. Again one can notice great choice of words in expressing the main plot of Navoi's sayings.

Conclusion: The large and unique heritage that S.N. Ivanov left us is one of the most significant resources in studying and developing the theory of translation and linguistics. Speaking about Sergei Nikolaevich, one cannot fail to note his excellent human qualities: high morality and decency, dedication to science, attentive and sensitive attitude towards colleagues, friendliness and tact in relations with students. Everyone with whom Sergei Nikolaevich communicated, had constant feelings of sympathy for him and deep respect.

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